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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

YOSHLAR NUTQIDA INTERNET VA IJTIMOY TARMOQLAR TA'SIRI

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JDPU Akademik litseyi ona tili va adabiyot fani o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning yoshlar nutqiga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot davomida sotsiologik so'rovnoma va kuzatuv metodlari qo'llanildi. Olingan natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, yoshlarning katta qismi qisqartmalardan, inglizcha so'z va atamalardan foydalanadi hamda internetdagi muloqot uslubi kundalik nutqqa ham ko'chib o'tmoqda. Ijtimoiy tarmoqlar yoshlar nutqini boyitishda ijobiy omil bo'lsa-da, u til madaniyati va adabiy me'yorlarga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi ham mumkin. Shuning uchun yoshlarning nutqiy madaniyatini mustahkamlash hamda internet muloqotida madaniy til me'yorlarini targ'ib qilish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: internet, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, yoshlar nutqi, qisqartmalar, inglizcha atamalar, nutqiy madaniyat, til me'yorlari

Kirish

Bugungi kunda internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlar yoshlarning kundalik hayotida eng faol ishlatiladigan kommunikatsiya vositalaridan biridir. Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi, xususan, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar (Telegram, Instagram, TikTok va boshqalar) yoshlarning til madaniyati va nutqiy xatti-harakatiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Ushbu jarayon natijasida yangi so'z va iboralar paydo bo'lishi, qisqartmalar, inglizcha atamalarni qo'llash hamda so'zlashuv nutqining o'zgarishi kuzatilmoqda. Maqolada internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning yoshlar nutqiga ta'siri ilmiy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi.

Metodologiya

Tadqiqot quyidagi metodlarga asoslandi:

- Sotsiologik so'rovnoma: 120 nafar 14–18 yoshdagi yoshlar ishtirok etdi.
- Kuzatuv metodi: ijtimoiy tarmoqlardagi yozishmalar va til birliklari tahlil qilindi.
- Taqqoslash va tahlil: adabiy til normalari bilan yoshlarning onlayn muloqotdagi nutqi solishtirildi.

Natijalar

So'rovnoma va kuzatuv natijalari quyidagilarni ko'rsatdi:

1. Ishtirokchilarning 82% internetda qisqartirilgan so'zlardan (masalan, "ok", "xmm", "btw") tez-tez foydalanadi.

2. 67% yoshlar inglizcha atamalarni o‘zbek nutqiga qo‘shib ishlatishini tan oldi (“like qilish”, “post tashlash”).
3. 55% yoshlar internetdagi so‘zlashuv uslubi ularning kundalik nutqiga ham ko‘chib o‘tishini bildirdi.
4. 43% ishtirokchi ijtimoiy tarmoqlar orqali nutqi boyiganini, yangi so‘zlarni tezroq o‘zlashtirganini qayd etdi.

1-diagramma. Yoshlar nutqiga internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlar ta’siri bo‘yicha so‘rovnoma natijalari

Muhokama

Olingan natijalar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlar yoshlarning nutq madaniyatiga ikki tomonlama ta’sir ko‘rsatmoqda:

- **Ijobiy ta’sir:** yangi so‘zlarning paydo bo‘lishi, chet tillaridan kirib kelayotgan terminlarni tezroq o‘zlashtirish, tezkor muloqot.
- **Salbiy ta’sir:** qisqartmalarning haddan tashqari ko‘pligi, adabiy til me’yorlarining buzilishi, so‘z boyligining sun’iy ravishda torayishi.

Demak, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar yoshlar uchun til taraqqiyoti manbai bo‘lishi bilan birga, til me’yorlarini saqlash masalasida muammolarni ham yuzaga keltirmoqda.

Xulosa

Internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlar yoshlarning nutqiy faoliyatida muhim o‘rin egallaydi. Bir tomondan, ular yoshlar nutqini boyitib, global axborot makoniga moslashishga yordam beradi. Boshqa tomondan, qisqartmalar, inglizcha aralashmalar va normadan chetlanish holatlari til madaniyatiga salbiy ta’sir qilmoqda. Shuning uchun ta’lim tizimida va ommaviy axborot vositalarida yoshlarning adabiy nutq madaniyatini mustahkamlash, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda ham madaniy muloqot qoidalarini targ‘ib qilish zarur.

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